

Synthesis of 5-arylidene-2-aryl-3-(2-chlorophenothiazinoacetamidyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones as antifungal and anticonvulsant agents

S. K. Srivastava*, S. L. Srivastava and S. D. Srivastava

Synthetic Organic Chemistry Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University,
Sagar-470 003, India

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Condensation of N^{10} -(acetohydrazido)-2-chlorophenothiazine (2) with various substituted aromatic aldehydes yields arylideneacetohydrazido-2-chlorophenothiazines (3) which on cycloaddition with mercaptoacetic acid afford the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones (4). Treatment of the 4-thiazolidinones with various substituted aromatic aldehydes afford 5-arylidene-2-aryl-3-(2-chlorophenothiazinoacetamidyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones (5). The compounds exhibit antifungal and anticonvulsant activities.

Phenothiazine derivatives possess potent biological activities¹. We reported earlier the synthesis and biological activity of compounds derived from phenothiazine nucleus^{2,3}. 4-Oxothiazolidines and their 5-arylidene derivatives also possess a variety of therapeutic activities⁴. The incorporation of 4-oxothiazolidines and their 5-arylidenes at 10th position in 2-chlorophenothiazine having a secondary amino group, used as the target for chemical modification (Scheme 1), has been found to enhance the activity. We have synthesised several new 2-chloropheno-thiazino-4-thiazolidinones and their 5-arylidenes. The compounds have been evaluated for their antifungal and anticonvulsant activities.

2-Chlorophenothiazine on electrophilic substitution by ethyl chloroacetate yielded ethyl N^{10} -2-chlorophenothiazinyl acetate (1). Compound 1 on amination with hydrazine hydrate afforded N^{10} -2-chlorophenothiazinylhydrazine (2) which on condensation with various substituted aromatic aldehydes yielded N^{10} -(phenylidenehydrazidomethyl)-2-chlorophenothiazine (3). Compound 3 on reaction with mercaptoacetic acid underwent dehydrative annulation to give 2-(substituted-aryl)-3-(N^{10} -2-chlorophenothiazinylacetamidyl)-4-oxothiazolidine (4) which on application of Knoevenagel reaction with various substituted aromatic aldehydes yielded 2-(substituted-aryl)-3-(N^{10} -2-chlorophenothiazinylacetamidyl)-5-arylidene-4-oxothiazolidines (5).

Antifungal activity: Compounds 4 and 5 were screened for their antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* (C.a), *Rizopus oryzae* (R.o), *Aspergillus niger* (A.n) and *Cryosporium pannical* (C.p), at 10° and 500 ppm concentrations using griseofulvin and dithane (M-45) as standards. The following compounds showed good activity against the fungi (in parenthesis) : 4c (C.a), 4g (C.a and A.n), 4i (R.o

Ar ¹	Ar ¹
a 2-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	f 4-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄
b 3-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	g 2-Br.C ₆ H ₄
c 4-Cl.C ₆ H ₄	h 3-Br.C ₆ H ₄
d 2-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	i 4-Br.C ₆ H ₄
e 3-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) NH₂NH₂, (ii) Ar¹CHO, (iii) mercaptoacetic acid, THF, (iv) Ar¹CHO, C₂H₅ONa.

and C.p), 4f 5e, 5g (C.a and R.o), 4h, 5i (A.n) and 5b (C.p).

Anticonvulsant activity : Compounds **4** and **5** (100 mg/kg bw) were screened for their anticonvulsant activity against pentylenetetrazole (90 mg/kg bw) induced convulsions in albino rats (30–40 g) of either sex by the reported method². Phenobarbitone was used as a reference drug at 50 mg/kg bw which was observed to protect 100% against the induced convulsions. Compounds **4g**, **4h**, **4i**, **5d**, **5g**, **5h** and **5i** provided 70, 80, 80, 70, 80, 80 and 70% protection.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. The purity of the compounds was monitored by tlc. All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Ethyl N¹⁰-2-chlorophenothiazinyl acetate (1) : A mixture of 2-chlorophenothiazine (0.1 mol) in dry Me₂CO (60 ml) and ethyl chloroacetate (0.1 mol) in the presence of anhyd. K₂CO₃ (5 g) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~10 h, then cooled and the solid obtained was dried and crystallized from EtOH (80%), m.p. 122–124° (Found : C, 60.00; H, 4.33; N, 4.32. C₁₆H₁₄O₂NSCl requires : C, 60.09; H, 4.38; N, 4.38%); ν_{\max} 1725 (C=O ester), 1460 cm⁻¹ (N-CH₂); δ 1.20 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.10 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, COOCH₂CH₃), 3.60 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 7.10–7.90 (7H, m, ArH).

N¹⁰-2-Chlorophenothiazine acetyl hydrazine (2) : A mixture of **1** (0.08 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.08 mol) in 1,4-dioxane (40 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~8 h, then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallized from methanol, (85%), m.p. 93–95° (Found : C, 54.85; H, 3.90; N, 13.71. C₁₄H₁₂ON₃SCI requires : C, 54.99; H, 3.92; N, 13.74%); ν_{\max} 3330 (NHNH₂), 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=O amido); δ 3.70 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.50 (2H, s, NH₂), 8.20 (1H, s, CONH), 7.20–7.90 (7H, m, ArH).

Arylidene acetohydrazido-2-chlorophenothiazine (3a) : A mixture of **2** (0.05 mol) in CHCl₃ (30 ml), 2-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.05 mol) and glacial acetic acid (4–5 drops) was refluxed on a water-bath for ~8 h, then cooled and evaporated to get a residue which was crystallized from ethanol, (80%), m.p. 118–120° (Found : C, 58.81; H, 3.47; N, 9.79. C₂₁H₁₅ON₃SCI₂ requires : C, 58.87; H, 3.50; N, 9.81%); ν_{\max} 3340 (NH), 1660 (C=O amido), 1620 cm⁻¹ (CH=N); δ 3.60 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.40 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.10 (1H, s, CONH), 7.10–7.90 (11H, m, ArH).

Likewise, other compounds (**3b-i**; yields 78–85%) were prepared by treating **2** with various aromatic aldehydes :

3b, m.p. 130–132°; **c**, 115–116°; **d**, 121–122°; **e**, 128–129°; **f**, 135–136°; **g**, 145–147°; **h**, 152–154°; **i**, 141–142°.

2-Aryl-3-(2-chlorophenothiazinoacetamidyl)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones (4a) : A mixture of **3a** (0.01 mol) in THF (30 ml) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.01 mol) with a pinch of anhydrous ZnCl₂, was refluxed for ~12 h on a water-bath. The separated solid was crystallized from methanol, (75%), m.p. 160–162°; (Found : C, 54.92; H, 3.32; N, 8.33. C₂₃H₁₇O₂N₃S₂Cl₂ requires : C, 54.98; H, 3.38; N, 8.36%); ν_{\max} 3350 (NH), 1710 (C=O cyclic), 1655 cm⁻¹ (C=O amidyl); δ 3.20 (1H, s, CH-N), 3.60 (2H, s, CH₂-S), 3.70 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 8.60 (1H, s, CONH), 7.10–7.90 (11H, m, ArH).

Similarly, **4b-i** (yields 69–78%) were prepared from **3b-i** using different aromatic aldehydes : **4b**, m.p. 172–173°; **c**, 168–170°; **d**, 179–180°; **e**, 156–158°; **f**, 140–142°; **g**, 165–166°; **h**, 171–172°; **i**, 168–169°.

5-Arylidene-2-aryl-3-(2-chlorophenothiazinoacetamidyl)-1,3-thiazolidine-4-ones (5a) : A mixture of **4a** (0.005 mol) and 2-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.005 mol) in dioxane (40 ml) in the presence of C₂H₅ONa, was refluxed for ~6 h, then cooled and the resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol, (69%), m.p. 188–190°; (Found : C, 57.60; H, 3.18; N, 6.70. C₃₀H₂₀O₂N₃S₂Cl₃ requires : C, 57.64; H, 3.20; N, 6.72%); ν_{\max} 3350 (NH), 1715 (C=O cyclic), 1650 (C=O amidyl), 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=CH-Ar); δ 3.20 (1H, s, CH-N), 3.70 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 5.20 (1H, s, C=CH-Ar), 8.50 (1H, s, CONH), 7.15–8.00 (15H, m, ArH).

Similarly, **5b-i** (yields 65–75%) were prepared from **4b-i** : **5b**, m.p. 200–201°; **c**, 192–193°; **d**, 184–185°; **e**, 205–207°; **f**, 178–179°; **g**, 195–196°; **h**, 188–190°; **i**, 210–212°.

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